

THE ROLE OF THE SERVICE IN TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract The role of service is eminently important in the development of any business. By providing great customer service, organizations can recover customer acquisition costs, retain talent, and foster brand loyalty. Without applying quality to the task or service, both the management and the foundation of the work suffer. Whether someone is traveling for work or leisure, they anticipate having a positive experience both during the trip and stay there. So, in this scientific article, we will discuss about the role of the service in tourism sphere.

Key words: service, business, leisure, experience, trip, tourism sphere, management

Абстракт Роль сервиса чрезвычайно важна в развитии любого бизнеса. Предоставляя отличное обслуживание клиентов, организации могут окупить затраты на привлечение клиентов, удержать талантливых специалистов и повысить лояльность к бренду. Без применения качества к задаче или услуге страдает как управление, так и основа работы. Независимо от того, путешествует ли кто-то по работе или на отдых, он ожидает получить положительные впечатления как во время поездки, так и во время пребывания там. Итак, в этой научной статье мы поговорим о роли сервиса в сфере туризма.

Ключевые слова: сервис, бизнес, досуг, опыт, поездка, сфера туризма, менеджмент

Abstrakt Har qanday biznesni rivojlantirishda xizmatning roli juda muhimdir. Mijozlarga katta xizmat ko'rsatish orqali tashkilotlar mijozlarni sotib olish xarajatlarini qoplashlari, iste'dodlarni saqlab qolishlari va brendga sodiqlikni rivojlantirishlari mumkin. Vazifa yoki xizmatga sifatni qo'llamasdan, menejment ham, ishning poydevori ham zarar ko'radi. Kimdir ish yoki dam olish uchun sayohat qiladimi, ular sayohat paytida ham ijobiy tajribaga ega bo'lishni kutishadi va u erda qolishadi. Shunday qilib, ushbu ilmiy maqolada biz xizmatning turizm sohasidagi o'rni haqida gaplashamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: xizmat, biznes, dam olish, tajriba, sayohat, turizm sohasi, menejment

Introduction

One of the most successful sectors today is travel and tourism, which is currently regarded as one of the most popular activities carried out for a variety of reasons. Everything is based on the organization's ability to provide high-quality services and work. As a result, it is crucial for businesses to provide consistent services. The reliability of the service guarantees that clients will choose the same travel agency when they return.

The components of travel services as identified under NAICS, exploring the function of each area and ways they interact:

1. Travel agencies
2. Online travel agencies (OTAs)
3. Tour operators
4. Destination marketing organizations (DMOs)
5. Other organizations

Following these definitions and descriptions, we'll take a look at some other support functions that fall under tourism services.

Travel agency

A company that acts as a middleman between the travel industry (provider) and the traveler is a travel agency (purchaser). One of the duty of the

travel agency is to sell bundled travel tours and holidays to potential travellers. The agency can also act as a middleman between the traveler and lodging, transportation providers, and tour operators (Goeldner & Ritchie, 2003). A small, privately held travel agency may be a component of a bigger organization.

A traveler who is planning to investigate and book activities and packages through an agency will first speak with a travel agent. Travel agents may focus on particular places, outdoor activities, backpacking, train travel, cruises, cycling, or gourmet tours, to mention a few.

Today, travellers have the option of researching and booking everything they need online without the help of a travel agent. As technology and the internet are increasingly being used to market destinations, people can now choose to book tours with a particular agency or agent, or they can be **fully independent travellers (FITs)**, creating their own itineraries.

Service recovery

Service recovery is all about righting your wrongs. This is the process of recovering from a poor customer service experience and regaining customer loyalty. The main thing is to react as quickly as possible and correct your mistakes when you notice them. Successful service recovery should restore the customer's trust, increase customer attention, and drive brand awareness.

According to Zendesk's Customer Experience Trends report, 80 percent of customers will leave after more than one disappointing service experience. Thus, if your customers have just two negative experiences with your support team, most of them will likely leave and go to competitors - which can have a devastating impact on your business. The recovery service is a chance to improve customer relations and increase their numbers even more. In fact, [Harvard Business Review](#) found that people who complained or wrote negative comments about a brand on social media and received a response were more loyal afterward than those who never complained at all. Many businesses are already working to restore customer service in some way, but without a clear process, they could miss a valuable opportunity.

Managers seeking to improve organizational capabilities related to service recovery should train and arm frontline employees with resources to take four critical steps immediately upon recognizing a service failure: 1) apologize, 2) listen, 3) resolve and follow up, and 4) document.

Realizing your mistake and asking for forgiveness for it will be a big plus for both the company and this employee and it will calm the upset client. Customers want to know that your company is on their side. So by taking responsibility for failures and showing customers that you and your company care about their well-being, your employees can focus on solving problems and regaining their trust and loyalty. But there are cases when an employee does not want to apologize for what they did not do, and it is very important to explain managers to them that an employee can always “sympathize” with a client experiencing distress, regardless of the cause of distress. Apologies should be seen as a sign of maturity and empathy; it is not always an admission of guilt. As a rule “The customer is always right”. Frontline employees should also recognize that they are the face of the company and that management counts on them to provide an apology on behalf of the organization.

When there is a problem with the service, employees should not blame customers or make judgments about what they say, but rather show appreciation for the information. It is important that customers feel heard. It is better to hear customer complaints directly than to read about them in the comments. Repeating customer complaints shows that the employee was listening to the customer correctly and initiates a conversation for the employee to find a solution.

Bringing the problem to a satisfactory solution and solving the problem quickly is a key factor to success. At the same time, employees should be empowered to make full use of the available tools. Important things that employees should know and have are 1) giving them right knowledge and skills, 2) providing them with the appropriate resources and/or budget (e.g., to compensate a wronged customer), 3) be able to use creativity and being problem solver.

Documenting conversations and resolving customer issues will help prevent similar situations from occurring in the future. Internally recording and communicating the history of relationships, such as service outages and restorations, gives team members the information they need to address the customer experience and can lead to more careful responses in subsequent interactions. There is a nature. By documenting service outages in detail and creating a closed feedback loop, organizations can identify vulnerabilities and implement steps to permanently remediate system errors.

Conclusion

With customer recovery, you can turn an unhappy customer into a loyal one. Also in practice you can see creating by own service recovery programs, leading brands like Birchbox and Williams-Sonoma have seen measurable improvements in customer sentiment.

Good service recovery requires hiring qualified and motivated people, providing them with the right resources, and regularly leading by leadership to demonstrate desired behavior. As with most things in business, the ethos of service recovery starts at the top.

The travel services industry is being compelled to develop at an astounding rate in a time when financial resources are scarce and competition for tourist dollars is fierce. By the time you read this, the landscape of travel services will probably have undergone a significant transformation due to the emergence of OTAs and the rapid rate of change.

20 years ago, a travel agent was essential for planning both pleasure and business trips, but today, anyone can quickly and easily book a trip over the phone. The future of this industry is both tough and intriguing.

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